

The Persuasive Power of Populist Frames: Who Is to Blame?

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Abstract

Common wisdom argues that populism has detrimental effects on democracy. However, if populism has such dangerous potential, then how can we explain the increasing acceptance of populist candidates and parties worldwide? Prior research suggests that this success is to be attributed to the use of populist rhetoric (Bos et al., 2020; Hameleers & Schmuck, 2017). However, it is yet to be established whether its persuasive effects differ depending on the type of frame - anti-elite, exclusionist. The anti-elite frame tends to blame political elites for socioeconomic issues, whereas the exclusionist frame finds the culprit in immigrants and minorities.

To address this gap, this study employs an online experiment ($N= 134$) to test whether (H1) anti-elite frames elicit a higher level of issue agreement about an economic issue – the decline of purchasing power of citizens - as compared to exclusionist and neutral frames. Moreover, it explores whether (H2) respondents' levels of populist attitudes moderate this relationship. With these expectations, this study aims to equip citizens with an understanding of the mechanisms of populist frames, helping them navigate information with a discerning eye. Results show that anti-elite frames are not more persuasive than exclusionist and neutral frames when covering the economic issue, and this also applies to respondents who score high on populist attitudes. Thus, going against Bos et al. (2020), Hameleers and Schmuck (2017), we cannot assume that anti-elite frames are effective in persuading individuals, independently of their preexisting populist attitudes.

Keywords: populism, framing, communication, blame attribution, schemata theory, social identity.

The Persuasive Power of Populist Frames: Who Is to Blame?

In today's political landscape, the names Giorgia Meloni, Donald Trump, Geert Wilders and Javier Milei linger prominently in the minds of the public, as they are gaining electoral success worldwide. Donald Trump was elected U.S. President in 2016, Giorgia Meloni was designated Italy's Prime Minister in 2022, and now the recent victories of the PVV during the 2023 Dutch elections and Javier Milei's nomination as president of Argentina further exemplify the rise of populism worldwide (Mudde, 2004).

But what is that makes these political actors so popular? Is there a feature they all share? The answer lies in their use of populist rhetoric. This communicative strategy stems from the core concept of populism, which was first defined by Mudde (2004) as a 'thin ideology' lacking a theoretical foundation and adapting to various political ideologies. Essentially, populism engages in a social conflict between the 'ordinary people', the political and economic 'elite' and the perceived 'outsiders' (Mudde, 2004). This concept can be interpreted as a social identity frame, stemming from social identity theory (Tajfel & Turner, 1986). This theory argues that individuals who identify with a group – in this case the 'ordinary people' – strive to safeguard their identity from outsiders (Mudde, 2004; Tajfel & Turner, 1986). Moreover, since there is a clear demarcation between social groups, blame attribution becomes another intrinsic populist characteristic, suggesting that individuals seek to identify causes of events, making attributions of possible scapegoats for their misfortunes – such as immigrants or the government (Busby et al., 2019).

Surprisingly, we know little about the mechanisms behind populist communication, as scholars have mostly examined populism from an actor-centric perspective, neglecting the discursive approach (Mudde, 2004; Zulianello et al., 2018). The latter views populism as a communication style that can be employed by any actor irrespective of their ideology and personality (Zulianello et al., 2018). Only recently, researchers have begun to employ this

approach to investigate the effects of populist frames, hence, messages that contain at least one populist feature (i.e., *people-centrism*, *anti-elitism*, *blame attribution towards outsiders*), (Bos et al., 2020; Busby et al., 2019). Yet, a significant bias persists with the neglect of left-wing frames, perpetuating the misconception that populism is only associated with the radical right (Casiraghi et al., 2023; March, 2017). In addition to this first scientific gap, most studies focus on the long-term effects of populist communication, overlooking potential short-term effects, such as citizens' level of agreement with the framed issue (see Bos et al., 2020; Schmuck & Matthes, 2017). Finally, a third shortcoming relates to the sender of the message. Too often scholars have limited their enquiry to politicians and parties, overlooking the media and citizens as populist communicators (Hameleers & Schmuck, 2017; Oliver & Rahn, 2016). Given the influential role of the media in shaping public perceptions and opinions, it becomes imperative to examine the effects of populist rhetoric on citizens, thereby preventing societal polarization (Bos et al., 2020; Hameleers et al., 2021). Against this backdrop, this study poses the following research question:

“To what extent does the use of frames (*anti-elite vs. exclusionist vs. neutral*) in a fictional news story, influence citizens' level of issue agreement for the economic threat presented in the news (*decline in purchasing power of citizens*), and how is this relationship moderated by the level of populist attitudes of participants?”.

In this study, the dependent variable ‘level of agreement’ pertains to how much participants agree with the economic topic outlined through an anti-elite, exclusionist, or neutral frame (Bos et al., 2021). As for the independent variable, the three conditions are interpreted as social identity frames, which can be conceptualized as emphasis frames (Hameleers et al., 2021). The anti-elite frame contains elements of people-centrism and anti-elitism, such as explicit reference to ‘the people’, and attacks on the corrupted and selfish ‘elites’ who are portrayed as a monolithic entity (March, 2017; Mudde, 2004). With a subtle

difference, exclusionist frames highlight the exclusionary attitude of ‘the people’, framing immigrants as ‘dangerous others’ (Zulianello et al., 2018). Finally, the neutral frame covers the decline of purchasing power objectively, without blaming a specific actor.

To further enhance this research, this study accounts for the moderator populist attitudes of participants. In this context, a populist attitude refers to individuals’ support for populist ideas, both against the ‘elite’ and/or ‘outsiders’ (Busby et al., 2019; Casiraghi et al., 2023). The inclusion of the moderator is supported by schema theory, which holds that when individuals encounter new information that aligns with their beliefs, they are naturally prone to accept that information and how it is framed (Hameleers et al., 2021). Thus, we assume that participants with high populist attitudes are more likely to accept populist frames, for they are congruent with their preexisting attitudes (Busby et al., 2019; Casiraghi et al., 2023; Hameleers et al., 2021). To fortify this enquiry, in the next section, we will dive into the theories that support the assumptions.

Theoretical framework

‘Either you’re with us, or you’re against us.’

This sentence is explanatory of the binary social division reported in populism (Bos et al., 2020). There is an appeal to the vulnerable ‘people’, viewed as a morally superior, homogeneous, and monolithic entity (Zulianello et al., 2018). At the same time, the other groups are defined either through vertical comparisons between ‘the people’ and the corrupted and selfish ‘elites’ (political, cultural, economic), and/or through horizontal comparisons between ‘the people’ and ‘outsiders’, such as immigrants and other minorities (Bos et al., 2020; Mudde, 2004; Zulianello et al., 2018). This social divide is grounded in social identity theory (Tajfel & Turner, 1986), which refers to individuals’ self-relatedness within a particular group (e.g., Spanish), and the emotional relevance associated with that membership (e.g., pride, collectiveness), (Tajfel, 1974). When individuals seek to be part of a

group, they adopt and adapt to the in-group identity; thus, norms, attitudes, and behaviours that distinguish them from external groups (Seyranian, 2014). Social identity theory also postulates that for a message to resonate with the public, it should be framed along the lines of the 'in-group' identity (Seyranian, 2014).

If we extend social identity to populist communication, left-wing parties promote themselves as the *vox populi*, engaging in anti-elite framing (March, 2017). Thus, their social identity frames outline the 'in-group' members as innocent and vulnerable and address the political and economic 'elites' as the culprits for the in-group's socio-economical issues, resonating with the 'in-group' identity (March, 2017). On the other hand, since radical right parties are rooted in nativism and nationalism, they appeal to their electorate through exclusionist messages that frame immigrants as threats to the security of the in-group as a nation (Bos et al., 2020; Busby et al., 2019; Gamson, 1992; March, 2017).

In line with the premises of social identity, this research explores the extent to which anti-elite, exclusionist and neutral frames produce issue agreement about the economic issue of declining purchasing power among citizens (Bos et al., 2020). Such an economic issue was chosen for three reasons. First, it addresses a contemporary economic challenge that impacts a considerable portion of the global population, making it an accessible subject of research. Second, this topic is highly versatile as it can be framed through an anti-elite, exclusionist, or neutral lens (Bos et al., 2020). Thirdly, the decline of the purchasing power of citizens is a strong factor in this historical 'representation gap' (Oliver & Rahn, 2016). This term refers to a historical and political condition when existing political parties are not responding to the needs of a large section of the electorate, namely the in-group (Oliver & Rahn, 2016). In this historical context, the economic threat triggers anger, disappointment, and resentment towards political representatives. This, in turn, facilitates the development of populist attitudes among citizens and paves the way for the emergence of populist actors. As citizens

seek to assign blame for their dissatisfaction, they simultaneously search for a champion who can restore their economic power.

As previous research revealed the influential power of blame attributions on attitudes, this research assumes that blame shifting plays a central role in determining the success of media populist frames on the level of issue agreement of citizens (Bos et al., 2020; Hameleers et al., 2016). This assumption is theoretically supported by attribution theory, which argues that individuals instinctively seek to understand the cause of events, making attributions of possible scapegoats (Busby et al., 2019). This process of attribution of responsibility is crucial for democratic functioning, as citizens can credit the government for its successes and blame it for its failures (Hameleers et al., 2016).

Blame-shifting is an intrinsic feature of populism as it defines the ‘elites’ and/or ‘outsiders’ as culprits for the perceived misfortunes of the ‘in-group’, giving them a clear target for their frustrations (Hameleers et al., 2016; Mudde, 2004). In line with this, the media can also generate populist framed messages, emphasizing certain features of reality instead of others (Hameleers et al., 2016). In this context, the media adopts the three features of populism (i.e., *people-centrism, conflict with the ‘elite’ and with ‘outsiders’*) and employs an emotionalized style that emphasizes anger and fear towards the ‘out-groups’ (Hameleers et al., 2016). Thus, in line with attribution theory, the media may use blame attribution as a frame element to cover economic issues, such as the decline of purchasing power of citizens (Busby et al., 2019; Hameleers et al., 2016).

Empirically, it has been shown that populist frames are more effective than neutral frames, as they give people a clear target for their frustrations while pointing to a solution (Busby et al., 2019). For example, a left-wing populist frame could suggest removing politicians from power to reduce the ‘in-group’ misfortunes (Busby et al., 2019).

This theoretical explanation is further supported by Bos et al. (2020), who showed that citizens are more likely to be lured into issue agreement if the news message is framed through populist lenses. In addition to this main finding, Bos et al. (2020) also discovered that citizens tend to reject the exclusionist frame if used to cover an economic threat. To reinforce this outcome, Schmuck and Matthes (2017) also report that economic threat messages are more persuasive if coupled with an anti-elite frame rather than an exclusionist frame. Drawing from social identity and blame attribution theories, we know that (1) populist frames foster issue agreement in respondents and that (2) anti-elite frames are more socially acceptable for citizens when covering an economic issue. Thus, this research expects that:

H1: The anti-elite frame (*left-wing*) will lead to a higher level of issue agreement about the decline of purchasing power of citizens in participants, as compared to an exclusionist frame (*right-wing frame*) and the neutral frame in news media.

While blame attribution proves to be a powerful communication strategy in persuading citizens, its effectiveness may vary among voters (Casiraghi et al., 2023). This is because the way individuals respond to a populist-framed message can be influenced by their preexisting political attitudes (Hameleers et al., 2021). This assumption is justified by schemata theory, which holds that when individuals encounter new information, they experience positive engagement with congruent information that aligns with their existing opinions on specific issues - making it easier to agree with the presented topic - but they experience internal conflict if exposed to incongruent information (Hameleers et al., 2021). In the realm of politics, this practice translates with the preferred political ideologies of citizens, which can influence the level of persuasion of populist frames and thus the level of issue agreement of participants (Dekeyser & Roose, 2023).

This concept is empirically supported by Van Hauwaert and Van Kessel (2017), who found that strong populist attitudes can motivate voters to support a populist party or

candidate, but only if they show congruent issue positions with the voters' opinions. In addition to this result, they found that citizens who place themselves at the middle of the political spectrum, hold below-average levels of populist attitudes since they view moderate parties as part of the political 'elite', rather than populist actors (Van Hauwaert & Van Kessel, 2017). As a result, they are less likely to be influenced by populist messages since they do not experience alignment between their political views and features of populist rhetoric.

Finally, Hameleers et al. (2021) reported a significant moderating effect of the political ideology of participants on the persuasiveness of 'anti-elite' frames. The results revealed that the persuasion of the 'anti-elite' frame is stronger for individuals with an extreme left-wing political ideology, proving that schemata theory is central to the persuasiveness of populist frames on citizens (Hameleers et al., 2021).

Against this backdrop, we can expect that:

H2: The anti-elite frame (*left-wing*) will lead to a higher level of issue agreement about the decline of the purchasing power of citizens in participants, as compared to an exclusionist frame (*right-wing frame*) and the neutral frame in news media; this effect is stronger for individuals with higher self-reported populist attitudes.

Figure 1

Conceptual Model

Method

Sample

To test the two hypotheses, experimental data was gathered via a Qualtrics online survey to a representative sample of global citizens above the age of 18 ($N = 134$). The sample was not restricted to one country since media populism and the decline of purchasing power are global phenomena, and the aim of this research is broad.

To estimate the number of participants for the experiment, a G*Power (3.1.3) analysis (Faul et al., 2009) was conducted before starting the sampling recruitment. An ANOVA f-test was conducted with a large ($\eta^2 = .25$) effect with $\alpha = .05$ and a power of .8 for three groups.

Results showed that the total sample to test the direct hypothesis was 159. The final sample obtained from data collection ($N = 201$) was reached after two weeks. After data cleaning, 67 units were excluded from the data set since they did not finish the questionnaire. This resulted in 134 participants ranging from 18 to 70 years old ($M = 31.10$, $SD = 16.25$), of which 40.3% were males, 58.2% were females, and only 2 participants selected respectively the ‘non-binary/third gender’ and the ‘prefer not to say’ conditions.

Participants were recruited through convenience sampling - snowballing - due to a lack of time and resources. Specifically, the sample was reached through social media platforms (Instagram, WhatsApp, LinkedIn), leveraging the online networks of the researcher and two of her colleagues. Participants were also encouraged to share the survey link with their network, aiming to reach participants with different political attitudes. After publishing the link for the first time, a reminder was sent two days later, one week later and on the last day of data collection.

Design

For this experiment, a 3-condition (typology of frame: anti-elite vs. exclusionist vs. neutral) between-subjects design was used. The hypotheses were tested through an online

experiment designed on Qualtrics. This method was the most suitable one, as it ensures ecological validity and allows to assess for causality. Moreover, since the experiment was online, it represents the most efficient solution compared to lab experiments. Nevertheless, there was a lack of control in the environment, which led to missed responses and other confounding effects (See Discussion).

Procedure

The online survey required approximately 7 minutes to complete. Responses were made anonymous, and participants were randomly assigned to conditions. Also, to ensure internal reliability, all blocks were forced responses.

The survey was distributed and made available for two weeks starting on the 17th of November 2023 until December 1st 2023. The questionnaire was structured in the following way. First, participants were required to read and complete the informed consent. Next, they would answer demographic questions related to their gender, age, nationality, and level of education, along with questions to identify the level of populist attitudes and their political ideology. Since the data collection was administered with two other students of the University of Amsterdam, an additional moderator 'citizens' level of trust in governmental institutions' and a mediator 'emotions' were included in the questionnaire, and later deleted from the data set because they were beyond the scope of this research. In the third section, respondents were randomly assigned to one of the three fictional news extracts, adapted from Bos et al. (2020). Next, participants were tested for the dependent variable level of issue agreement. One question serving as a manipulation check was added at the end of the questionnaire, after which participants were thanked for their participation and debriefed about the content of the experiment.

Research material

The questionnaire and stimulus materials were written in English to facilitate the understanding of the message across nationalities. The stimulus material was obtained from the already existing manipulations of Bos et al. (2020), (Figure 3, 4, 5 in Appendix B). The three conditions shared the same layout of a traditional news template and topic: the declining purchasing power of citizens (Bos et al., 2020). The news post consisted of an image with a wallet and a hand, signifying the topic of purchasing power. In all conditions, to avoid bias in the responses, Bos et al. (2020) created a fictional source called 'FutureNow'. The three conditions only differed for the frame. The first condition was characterized by anti-elite cues such as blaming the political 'elite' for the decline of purchasing power. In the exclusionist frame, immigrants were blamed for taking away resources from the hardworking native 'people', causing the decline of purchasing power (Bos et al., 2020). Finally, the neutral frame presented the economic issue with facts and arguments without blame attributions.

Measures

To measure the dependent variable level of issue agreement, respondents were asked to what extent they agreed with the statements – 'The economy will face a decline in the near future' ($M = 4.70$, $SD = 1.37$), 95 % CI [4.47, 4.93]; 'Immigrants are to blame for the decline of purchasing power of citizens' and 'Politicians are responsible for the decline of the purchasing power of citizens' - on a scale from 1 (*Completely disagree*) to 7 (*Completely agree*), (Bos et al., 2020), (Appendix A). The second and third statements were later removed in SPSS, for they did not measure what was intended to measure, hence, the level of agreement that there is a decline in purchasing power. The implementation of a 7-point Likert scale served to increase the internal validity of the measurement.

The moderator 'populist attitude' was assessed before stimulus exposure to avoid confounding effects. It was measured on a 7-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (*Completely*

disagree) to 7 (*Completely agree*) with four items measuring participants' level of anti-elitism - 'It doesn't really matter whom you vote for because the rich control both political parties' ($M = 3.33, SD = 1.79$); 'Politics usually boils down to a struggle between the people and the powerful' ($M = 4.41, SD = 1.47$); 'The system is stacked against people like me' ($M = 3.29, SD = 1.52$); 'People at the top usually get there from some unfair advantage' ($M = 4.44, SD = 1.62$) - and four items measuring the level of exclusionist attitudes - 'Immigrants cost our country a lot of money that should rather be invested in our own people' ($M = 2.84, SD = 1.61$); 'Immigrants are responsible for a lot of our nation's problems' ($M = 2.43, SD = 1.47$); 'Social benefits such as unemployment benefits and health insurance benefits are given to people who don't really deserve it' ($M = 3.31, SD = 1.61$); 'Our borders should be closed to immigrants' ($M = 2.12, SD = 1.32$). The first four items were drawn from the scale of Oliver and Rahn (2016), whereas the items measuring exclusionist attitudes were selected from the scale developed by Hameleers and Schmuck (2017).

A principal axis factor analysis (PAF) with direct oblimin showed that the 8 items measuring the populist attitude of participants form two latent constructs. Two components have an eigenvalue above 1 (eigenvalue 2.80; eigenvalue 2.41) and there is a clear point of inflexion in the scree plot. Together, these factors explain 65.16% of the variance in the original items. After a direct oblimin rotation, the first four items measuring anti-elite attitudes correlate positively with the second factor, whereas the four items measuring anti-immigrant attitudes correlate positively with the first factor. The reliability of the scale is acceptable, with Cronbach's alpha = .72. Therefore, it appears the scale measures the populist attitudes of citizens. Overall, participants scored in the middle of the scale ($M = 3.27$), showing no preexisting populist attitudes.

Also for the dependent variable – level of agreement of citizens - a principal axis factor analysis (PAF) with direct oblimin was run. The results showed that the three items

measuring the level of issue agreement of citizens form a single uni-dimensional scale: only one component has an eigenvalue above 1 (eigenvalue 1.39) and there is a clear point of inflexion after this component in the scree plot. This factor explains 46.39% of the variance in the original items. The reliability of the scale is not acceptable, with Cronbach's alpha = .41. Thus, the two items (1) blaming immigrants and (2) blaming politicians were removed from the scale of the dependent variable. These items proved to be incoherent with the purpose of this research, which is to examine whether anti-elite frames can produce more agreement in citizens about the existence of the economic threat, rather than measuring if citizens agree on who is responsible for the issue.

Manipulation checks

As for the manipulation check, all participants were asked: “According to the news story you read, who is to blame for the decline in purchasing power of citizens?” with multiple answer categories: ‘politicians’, ‘immigrants or ‘none of the above’.

The chi-square test $\chi^2(4, N = 134) = 64.25, p < .001$ confirmed that the material was recognized by participants. 53.2% ($N = 25$) of respondents correctly identified the exclusionist frame, 56.5% ($N = 26$) identified the neutral condition, and 73.2% ($N = 30$) recognized the anti-elite frame. The rest of the participants did not recognize the manipulations, as 49.9 % of them did not distinguish the neutral condition ($N = 22$), only one did not recognize the exclusionist frame ($N = 1$), and 64.8 % failed to recognize the anti-elite frame ($N = 30$).

Randomization checks

Randomization was also successful for gender, $\chi^2(6, N = 134) = 9.91, p = .129$, nationality, $\chi^2(32, N = 134) = 28.96, p = .621$, and level of education, $\chi^2(8, N = 134) = 5.59, p = .693$. Since every background variable was distributed equally across conditions, they were not included in the final analyses as covariates.

Results

This study was set up to explore the persuasive effects of populist frames on the level of issue agreement of citizens and how their populist attitudes could moderate this relationship.

The first hypothesis (H1) predicted that the anti-elite frames would lead to a higher level of issue agreement about the decline of the purchasing power of citizens, as compared to an exclusionist and neutral frame in news media. To test this hypothesis, a one-way ANOVA was run on SPSS. The analysis of variance showed a non-significant effect of the type of frame on the level of agreement of citizens $F(2, 133) = 0.14, p = .869, \eta^2 = .00$ with an absent effect size. The Bonferroni Post Hoc test did not indicate significant persuasive differences between the neutral frame ($M = 4.76, SD = 1.29$) and the exclusionist frame ($M = 4.72, SD = 1.25$), $p = 1.000$, and between the anti-elite and neutral frame ($M = 4.61, SD = 1.60$), $p = 1.000$. Finally, there was also no significant difference between the exclusionist frame and the anti-elite stimuli, $p = 1.000$. Thus, this first finding hinders the significant results of Bos et al. (2020) and Schmuck and Matthes (2017) who instead found support for the higher level of persuasiveness of *anti-elite* frames when presenting a socio-economic issue. This lack of significant results is potentially due to social desirability effects given the online setting of the experiment, and a small sample size ($N = 134$). Such limitations are further discussed in the following section.

The second hypothesis (H2) predicted that the persuasive effect of the anti-elite frame would be stronger for individuals who score high on populist attitudes, as suggested by Van Hauwaert and Van Kessel (2017). To test this hypothesis, a moderation analysis was conducted using SPSS's PROCESS macro v4.1 (Hayes, 2022). Overall results showed that there is no moderating effect of populist attitudes on the level of agreement of participants, $F(3, 130) = 0.28, p = .84$, with an absent effect size of $R^2 < .00$. The interaction between the

type of frame and populist attitude was not significant, with $b = 0.13$, $SE = 0.17$, $t(130) = .76$, $p = .451$, indicating that the relationship between the type of frame and level of issue agreement was not moderated by participants' level of populist attitudes (See Figure 2).

This was anticipated by the descriptive data of the scale measuring populist attitudes. The four items measuring exclusionist attitudes had below-average values ($M = 3.27$), showing no strong right-wing populist attitudes in participants. Similarly, respondents scored near the mean for the items measuring anti-elite attitudes, showing a slightly skewed left-wing populist attitude. These moderate responses can be explained by social desirability and conformity effects, which inhibit individuals from expressing their true opinions.

Figure 2

Interaction effect 'populist attitude' and 'type of frame'

In conclusion, given the insignificant effects for both H1 and H2, this study retains the null hypothesis that anti-elite frames do not lure citizens into more issue agreement as compared to exclusionist and neutral frames, and this does not differ for participants with populist attitudes.

Conclusion and Discussion

The corrosion of global democracy is fueled by the growing resentment towards 'elites' and 'outsiders,' contributing to a deeper polarization and fragmentation of society (Sandel, 2020). In this fragile socio-political context, populist actors emerge as champions of the common people, rejecting external groups. To communicate their mission, populist politicians, along with the media, rely on populist frames that emphasize the needs and desires of citizens while discriminating against elites and outsiders. Given the influential role of the media in shaping public perceptions and opinions, it becomes crucial to analyze the mechanisms of this populist rhetoric and understand its potential persuasiveness on citizens, thereby preventing further polarization. Consequently, this research aims to contribute to both scientific and societal knowledge by exploring the subtle differences between the types of populist frames and their persuasive impact on citizens (Bos et al., 2021; Hameleers & Schmuck, 2017).

First, this experiment was set to explore the persuasive effects of anti-elite frames on citizens' agreement about the decline of purchasing power. Second, it assumed respondents' populist attitudes could strengthen this relationship. Despite past research providing significant results, the hypotheses for this study were insignificant (Bos et al., 2020; Casiraghi et al., 2023; Hameleers & Schmuck 2017). In the first case, the anti-elite frame did not result in being more persuasive as compared to the other two conditions, unlike suggested by Bos et al. (2020). At the same time, the persuasiveness of the anti-elite frame did not significantly differ when adding the populist attitudes of participants as a moderator, such that the level of issue agreement neither decreased nor increased. Nevertheless, since previous research had significant effects, it is recommended to read the studies conducted by Bos et al. (2020), Casiraghi et al. (2023), and other researchers mentioned in this paper (Hameleers et al., 2021; Zulianello et al., 2018).

Finally, for a comprehensive understanding of the limitations of this research, it is crucial to acknowledge and address the shortcomings that impacted the results. First and foremost, the lack of reliability of the scale measuring the ‘level of issue agreement’ of participants. This is explained by two reasons. First, only after collecting data, we realized that the three items measured different dimensions. Specifically, the items ‘Immigrants are to blame for the decline of purchasing power of citizens’ and ‘Politicians are responsible for the decline of the purchasing power of citizens’ did not measure the level of agreement with the topic, but rather blame attribution, which is beyond the scope of this research. Another reason why the scale was not reliable is that only the ‘Economy will face a decline in the near future [...]’ was obtained from an existing scale by Bos et al. (2020), whereas the two other items were crafted by the researchers. As shown earlier in the method section, the solution adopted to optimize the results was to remove the two irrelevant items measuring blame attribution and limit the dependent variable to the item measuring the economic decline from the scale of Bos et al. (2020).

A second major limitation stems from the use of a convenience sampling strategy. The snowballing technique is known for its intrinsic flaw in generating a diverse and unbiased sample, posing challenges to the generalizability of results. This is evident in the skewed responses for the moderator ‘populist attitudes’ (Casiraghi et al., 2023). The recruitment of respondents through personal networks introduces the possibility of a homogeneous group sharing similar political views, compromising the study's external validity. Moreover, since the experiment was administered online, individuals without Internet access were automatically excluded, potentially introducing selection bias.

Thirdly, the left-wing skewness in responses related to the populist attitudes of participants may have been magnified by social conformity effects (Van Der Pligt & Vliek, 2017). Self-report measures, such as those used in our study, carry the risk of response bias,

as participants can provide socially desirable responses to align with perceived social norms. In this case, individuals possibly adjusted their responses to avoid appearing too politically extreme (Casiraghi et al., 2023), resulting in moderate populist attitudes.

A further methodological limitation concerns the lack of a pilot study or pre-test. This shortcoming might have been a factor determining the lack of reliability for the dependent variable scale; thus, we recommend future scholars conduct pre-tests to ensure the reliability of measurement instruments. Unfortunately, time constraints prevented us from implementing it in this study.

Lastly, due to a lack of time and resources, we did not manage to explore this topic with a longitudinal study and had to adapt to the usage of an online experiment. To improve the reliability and generalizability of future research in the domain of political communication, we propose the adoption of probability sampling techniques. Furthermore, incorporating multiple control variables alongside populist attitudes (e.g., frequency of exposure to news and voting behaviour) can provide a more extensive understanding of the variables at play.

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Appendix A – Questionnaire

Dear participant,

This survey was developed for educational purposes for the Graduation project at the University of Amsterdam. Participation in this survey will take less than 10 minutes.

The anonymity of your responses is ensured and you may quit the survey at any time. If you do not want to participate in this experiment after having completed the survey, you may contact the researcher and withdraw from the study within 24 hours.

I hereby declare that I fully and voluntarily agree to participate in this research study. With this, I retain the right to withdraw my consent, without having to give a reason for doing so. I know I may halt my participation in the experiment at any time. If my research results are used in scientific publications or made public in another way, this will be done so that my anonymity is completely safeguarded. My data will not be passed on to third parties without my permission. If I wish to receive more information about the research, either now or in future, I can contact Felisa Ferroglio via felisa.ferroglio@student.uva.nl.

- I understand the text presented above, and I agree to participate in the research study.
- I understand the text presented above. I do NOT agree and will not participate in the research study.

Block 1- Demographics

1) What is your gender?

Please select the category that represents you the most.

- Male
- Female
- Non-binary/third gender
- Prefer not to say

2) What is your age?

Please, write your age in numbers (example: 18).

3) What is your nationality?

If you have multiple, please select the one that represents you the most.

4) What is your highest level of completed education?

- High school Diploma
- Undergraduate Degree
- Master Degree
- PhD
- Other

Block 2 – Moderators and control variables

1) In politics, people talk of 'Liberalism' and 'Conservatism'.

Where would you place yourself on the following slide, where 0 means 'Conservative' and 10 means 'Liberal'?

(Slider from 0 = Conservative political position, to 7 = Liberal political position)

2) On a 7-point scale ranging from "Strongly disagree" to "Strongly agree", to what extent do you agree with the following statements?

- I think the government is interested in my well-being.
- I think the government is truthful in its dealings with me.
- I think the government is competent and effective.

3) On a 7-point scale ranging from "Strongly disagree" to "Strongly agree", to what extent do you agree with the following statements?

- It doesn't really matter who you vote for because the rich control both political parties.
- Politics usually boils down to a struggle between the people and the powerful.

- The system is stacked against people like me.
- People at the top usually get there from some unfair advantage.
- Immigrants cost our country a lot of money that should rather be invested in our own people.
- Immigrants are responsible for a lot of our nation's problems.
- Social benefits such as unemployment benefits and health insurance benefits are given to people who don't really deserve it.
- Our borders should be closed to immigrants.

Block 3 – Conditions

In the next section, you will be exposed to an online news story. Please, take your time to analyze it and then answer the following questions.

(On the next page):

One of the three stimuli is shown randomly to participants for 30 seconds. Each stimulus is presented with the following statement: You will be able to move to the next question in 30 seconds. (for the stimuli material, see Appendix B).

Block 4 – Dependent variable

After reading the presented news story, to what extent do you agree with the following statements?

Please select your level of agreement on this 7-point scale ranging from 'Strongly disagree' to 'Strongly agree'.

- The economy will face a decline in the near future, starting with the decline of the purchasing power of citizens.
- Politicians are responsible for the decline of the purchasing power of citizens.
- Immigrants are to blame for the decline of the purchasing power of citizens.

Block 5 – Mediator

After reading about the decline of the purchasing power of citizens, please indicate to what extent you experience the following feelings, ranging from "Not at all" to "Very much".

- Rage
- Powerlessness
- Accomplishment
- Confidence

Block 6 – Manipulation check

According to the news story you read, who is to blame for the decline in purchasing power of citizens?

- Politicians
- Immigrants
- None of the above

Block 7 – Debriefing

Thank you for your participation!

This research aims to examine to what extent populist frames (left-wing vs right-wing) can influence the level of issue agreement of citizens about the decline of purchasing power.

As part of this experiment, you were randomly assigned to one of the three fictional conditions. Please, be aware that the information in this survey was manipulated for the purpose of the study. If you have any feedback or questions regarding this research, feel free to contact one of the following researchers:

Felisa Ferroglio at felisa.ferroglio@student.uva.nl

Ilinca Parlea at ilincaparlea@student.uva.nl

Alisa Gladkova at alisa.gladkova@student.uva.nl

Appendix B – Stimulus material

Figure 3

Note. By Bos et al., 2020, anti-elite frame condition.

Figure 4

Note. By Bos et al., 2020, exclusionist frame condition.

Figure 5

Note. By Bos et al., 2020, neutral frame condition.